

DigiVet - Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

WP1 - Deliverable 1.3 - Denmark Danish stakeholder workshop

Authors:

Matthew Denwood¹, Søren Saxmose Nielsen¹, Peter Sandøe, Francisco Calvo Artavia²

¹ University of Copenhagen, Denmark

² Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, Denmark

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Introduction

The DigiVet project “Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health”, funded by NordForsk, is a three-year project running between 2021 – 2023, involving the countries United Kingdom, Denmark, Sweden, Norway and Estonia. DigiVet is composed of three work packages (WP), where the first, WP1, investigated the current opportunities, investments, and challenges regarding digitalisation of livestock data. The project also consists of three different case studies (CS), including CS1 (food safety), with particular emphasis on *Salmonella*, CS2 (health security), with focus on antimicrobial use (AMU), and CS3 (economic security), focusing on transboundary spread of African Swine Fever (ASF). A full introduction to Deliverable 1.3, within Task 1.3 “Stakeholders perception of current challenges/opportunities and knowledge gaps” (WP1), is given in the report “DigiVet – UK Stakeholder Workshop”.

This report is the Danish sub-report of Deliverable 1.3. In Denmark, this task was resolved by a physical workshop on 12th January 2023, which was held across all CS and involving all relevant stakeholders. We note that the timescale originally planned for the WP1 workshops was Q1-Q3 2022, so the workshop was held around 6 months behind schedule. This was due to the unforeseen impact of the Covid-19 epidemic and the desire to hold the meeting physically rather than online, which would not have been possible earlier. Despite this delay, activities in WP2 relating to each case study were able to proceed on schedule due to earlier discussions with relevant stakeholders, many of which were reflected in findings from the workshop presented below.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework used as a basis for the workshops is explained in more detail in the DigiVet Deliverable 1.2¹. The framework was adapted from Zhang et al. (2022), defining different components of the data lifecycle (Figure 1). Challenges and opportunities to digitalise data and finding new technical solutions in relation to the data lifecycle were investigated from societal, technological, environmental, economic, and political (STEEP) perspectives.

Figure 1 - The data lifecycle, adapted from Zhang et al. (2022)

¹ Deliverable 1.2 is published at: <https://zenodo.org/record/7440884>

Identification of Stakeholders

Relevant stakeholders were identified and recruited for participation in both interviews and the workshop, using snowballing to broaden the network of participants where necessary. The starting point for the snowballing process was taken from the professional contacts of the Danish DigiVet team and their immediate colleagues. The primary organisations targeted were as follows:

- The Danish Food and Veterinary Administration, who have overall responsibility for animal health and welfare in Denmark (including diseases of livestock, food safety and antimicrobial usage).
- The Danish academic/university sector, including the University of Copenhagen (housing Denmark's only veterinary school) and Denmark's Technical University (who are involved with research into food safety).
- SEGES Innovation, an independent and not-for-profit organisation that is owned and run by the Danish farming community.
- The Danish Agriculture and Food Council, who represent the farming and food industry of Denmark.

Invitations to the workshop were initially sent to specifically targeted individuals within different teams of these organisations, with the request to pass along the invitation to the most suitable individuals that would be able to attend on the specified date. The general response to the invitation was very positive, with one or more relevant individuals from all targeted groups/organisations accepting the invitation to attend.

A total of 19 stakeholders from five organizations attended the workshop, along with 6 organizers (DigiVet team members, note takers and a facilitator). A full breakdown is given in Appendix 1.

Workshop Format

The workshop was structured in a similar manner to the UK WP1 workshop that had been held approximately 6 months previously; this involved a mixture of small group (pairs/threes) brainstorming followed by a plenary discussion on a series of specific topics. Upon arrival, the stakeholders were asked to seat themselves at four large round tables – delegates from the same organisation were encouraged to divide themselves across different tables where possible, and a note taker / facilitator was seated at each table. The meeting was held in English, but native Danish speaking stakeholders were encouraged to give their input in Danish, where this was necessary in order to facilitate communication of difficult/technical concepts. A member of the DigiVet team served as facilitator; explaining the purpose and the rules of workshop, ensuring that time was kept, and helping to summarise points made by the workshop participants.

The session began with an introduction to the DigiVet project, noting the blend of social science and computer science / epidemiology involved, and emphasising the focus on the lifecycle of digital data. The goals for the day were outlined, and the “house rules” clearly defined as follows:

- The primary purpose of the workshop was to gather a diverse range of opinions and perspectives rather than to reach a consensus. Disagreement was therefore encouraged, although participants were asked to keep the tone of discussions civil and respectful.
- The workshop was conducted under the Chatham House Rule i.e. notes of discussion topics were made during the workshop, and a report subsequently circulated to attendees, but these notes/report do NOT reveal the identity or affiliation of individuals in relation to specific comments.
- Participation was voluntary and stakeholders were free to withdraw at any time.

The participants were shown the detailed agenda for the day (Appendix 2), including the specific questions that they would be asked, and were introduced to the workshop format including use of post-it notes. The different case studies were briefly outlined to provide context for the more specific discussions timetabled. The stakeholders were specifically asked to consider the following points during the day:

- Constraints related to data acquisition, aggregation, management, use or benefits of digital data records for livestock health and welfare.
- Other key factors affecting digital adoption on farms, markets, abattoirs, or other relevant sites.
- Ethical, legal, and regulatory issues which may affect public or stakeholder opinion, trust and return value of digital data - including privacy protection and data sharing policies.
- Opportunities to strengthen digitalisation of the livestock sector to improve surveillance and health and welfare.

An informal round-table introduction was then taken in order to allow the stakeholders to get a complete overview of the participants in the workshop: this was partly done to encourage the stakeholders to feel more comfortable in sharing information and opinions within a safe environment. As part of this process, the stakeholders were also asked to briefly (in less than 1 minute each) summarise their major concerns and future wishes with respect to digitalisation of livestock data. A thematic summary of these follows below.

Concerns

- Data accessibility
 - Structural barriers (i.e. accessibility).
 - Difficulty of using data for research.
 - Lack of resources for sharing data between stakeholders.
- Data quality
 - Missing information.
 - Issues with collection.
 - Incorrect recordings.
- Use of data
 - Lack of understanding of the origin of data and how missing/incorrect registration can occur.
 - Misusage and/or misinterpretation.
 - Lack of knowledge on how to use/interpret data.
- Communication

- Lack of interdisciplinary collaboration.
- Miscommunication of the meaning of data and/or results.
- Lack of follow-up on how the use of data has impacted policy e.g. AMU.

Wishes

- Collaboration
 - Increased cooperation between stakeholders.
 - More interdisciplinary work between stakeholders (including internationally).
 - Better data accessibility.
- Use of data
 - Better knowledge/training resources for users of data.
 - Ensure that results of analyses are communicated back to data providers.
 - Improved use of data to inform decision making.
 - Increased use of the available data in general.

Discussion 1: *what is working well and what challenges do we have with livestock data?*

The stakeholders were asked to spend 25 minutes in small groups writing post-it notes on their general opinion/experience of the current use of livestock data. These notes were then brought to two large whiteboards at the front of the room and organised into themes within the general areas of “working well” vs. “challenges”. These themes were then discussed in more depth during a 50-minute facilitated discussion, with notes being made during the discussion. The thematic summary below represents an amalgamation of the written notes made during the session as well as a post-hoc assessment of the key points raised on the post-it notes themselves.

Working well

- Data availability
 - The Danish “Centrale Husdyrbrugsregister” (central livestock registry; CHR) was conceived as, and is legislated to be, a public data source. There is therefore a legal requirement to enter, store and use data.
 - In general, a lot of livestock data are public in Denmark, and this can continue, provided that we prevent/avoid stigmatisation of farmers based on the data they make available.
 - There is a strong tradition of collaboration and positive attitude to sharing data within Denmark. It is important to teach students how to share data securely and responsibly.
- Data quality
 - Denmark has extremely high-quality data relative to most other countries.
 - This is partly due to a long history of collaboration between stakeholders, which must be continued to preserve the quality of data.

Challenges

- Motivation
 - Individual farmers (and vets) often do not understand the reason for entering data and do not see any direct results/benefit from the registration of data.

- Keeping track of the complex rules and requirements for reporting is very time-consuming, so farmers tend to prioritise compliance where they see the greatest need/importance.
 - There is a perceived danger of judgement and/or negative consequences for farmers that register data reflecting e.g. high use of antimicrobials.
 - The major requirement is on farmers to ensure that online data registration is correct (even if this was not entered by them directly) – this can be time consuming and degrades motivation when data are registered incorrectly.
 - Registration of data is a lower priority than caring for animals on the farm – both for farmers and for vets.
 - There is no real reward for farmers to make high-quality data registrations.
- Data quality
 - Data don't always reflect reality e.g. vets can deliberately register an inaccurate diagnosis so that they are able to prescribe the treatment they think is best (to work around the new Animal Health Law). Pressure to reduce usage of antimicrobials may also affect prescribed duration of treatments. It is important to remember the reason for data registration when working with the data.
 - Sometimes databases need to be changed to account for changes in the real world (new fields or changed structure) but in general documentation for these changes is absent or of poor quality.
 - Documentation styles/culture can vary between different institutions/workplaces e.g. one slaughterhouse may interpret meat quality differently than another.
 - Almost all data are subject to potential human mistakes, so it is important to be critical of the data.
 - Data processes
 - Internal database/anonymised IDs often need to be linked with e.g. CHR numbers when data are used – sometimes these lookup tables are not provided with the data. This is a particular challenge when merging databases collected at different levels.
 - Uncertainty regarding GDPR process has been a challenge, but currently GDPR is not being applied to most livestock data.
 - Sometimes data need to be pseudonymised / anonymised but there are not always resources to be able to do this.
 - We are missing mechanisms to routinely link/combine animal production data with public health data, for example AMU / AMR regulations affecting public health.
 - Documentation of the origin of data needs to be improved. Also, error corrections within databases are often done manually and sometimes without recording the time/date and reason for the correction.
 - Changes in how data are registered should be better recorded along with the data themselves, but there are not always resources to be able to do this in practice.
 - Sometimes identifiers (e.g. CHR) are re-used, causing different herds to be registered with the same identifiers at different times – we therefore need stricter one-time usage policies for identifiers.
 - Data sharing and data security

- Some data are classified as environmental, in order to become public data (e.g. MRSA in pigs).
- It is frequently experienced that projects/studies are not viable if there is a need to have data accessible at herd level.
- Legal problems are becoming more of a challenge – for example GDPR is currently a hot topic. Lawyers often do not agree with each other, which prevents progress being made.
- One authority may ask a question that requires data from another authority to be able to answer, but sometimes the data cannot be obtained.
- Access to data may be more restricted if the results of the data analysis are planned to become public.
- Manufacturers with commercial interests (e.g. with milking machines) do not share data, and dairies are also beginning to withhold data by default.
- There are challenges with how data are shared, particularly across different sectors. This limits the crucial final step of the data lifecycle, i.e. usage of the data.

Discussion 2: *what are the potential solutions for the problems we face?*

The second discussion session followed a similar format to the first. The stakeholders were asked to spend 25 minutes in small groups writing post-it notes summarising potential problems for the challenges raised in the first discussion session (note: the original schedule also included an elucidation of the root causes in this session, but this element was dropped as we felt it had been covered in the first discussion session). These notes were then brought to two large whiteboards at the front of the room and organised into themes, which were then discussed in more depth during a 50-minute facilitated discussion. The thematic summary below represents an amalgamation of the written notes made during the session as well as a post-hoc assessment of the key points raised on the post-it notes themselves.

- Data quality: motivation for better input
 - Data input should be automated as much as possible, and nobody should ever be asked to enter the same data twice into different systems.
 - Merging of databases should be done as early as possible in the pipeline so that errors can be caught closer to the source.
 - Some type of recognition (e.g. financial) could be provided to data providers for high-quality data. Focus on motivation is important.
 - Financial penalties could also be used for poor-quality data, where appropriate. This has proved to be successful in other applications.
 - We should avoid calculating the same data multiple times for different uses – a single data collection should be shared and distributed as appropriate.
 - Slaughterhouses could explore the use of AI to minimise human mistakes.
 - Education for relevant professionals (vets and pharmacists etc) should include more on data handling, in order to reduce future errors.
 - Research results should be communicated back to stakeholders (farmers and vets) so that they feel part of “the whole data chain”.

- The upcoming “DANISH boksen”² may help to reduce the number of different demands on farmers.
 - Databases should be compared regularly as an external verification exercise. Comparison of metrics to other countries can also be useful.
 - Farmers may respond well to friendly competition – we could potentially use informal “league tables” to encourage this.
- Documentation
 - We must avoid the situation where “institutional knowledge” is placed with a single person, as this makes data processes extremely vulnerable to losing knowledge. Redundancy in both capacity and knowledge is required.
 - A certain amount of “learning by doing” is required – this should be accounted for when hiring new individuals.
 - Processes should be put in place so that when relevant law/regulations change, information is logged in the database regarding when this change occurred as well as the expected impact on how data collection/quality may be affected.
 - Modernisation of databases must also include finance/resource for creating documentation – this is frequently forgotten.
 - Research increasingly requires data to be open and high quality – this may drive improvements.
 - Providing courses for calibration would be useful to ensure that the recorded data reflects real life.
 - Creating and maintaining good documentation requires resources (time and money), which is a fundamental challenge.
 - Balance of data security/accessibility
 - Collaboration agreements are essential – challenges are both legal AND technical. It is important for these agreements to stipulate what will NOT be done with the data as well as what WILL be done with the data.
 - Sharing data is easier to manage if the individuals accessing the data are stationed with the authority owning/maintaining the data.
 - Relevant authorities / stakeholders are currently working on ways to facilitate data sharing and access, working within existing outline agreements (Danish term: “rammeaftaler”).
 - We need standardised mechanisms and contracts for data access (specifically noting what data are shared, and what data are not shared, along with the relevant reasons/purposes). A cross-institute working group to create and maintain these would be very useful.
 - Improvements to security are incremental i.e. a process that evolves over time.
 - Lawyers lack technical understanding of the data, so it is usually better to ask specific questions about contracts/agreements than more general questions about what is possible. Contracts should detail the use of the data.

² https://svineproduktion.dk/Viden/Paa-kontoret/Love-regler-og-standarder/Danish_boksen

Case study-specific discussions

Following the more general discussions, three case-study specific discussion sessions were held to focus on issues specifically relating to *Salmonella* Dublin, African Swine Fever (ASF), and antimicrobial usage (AMU). The format of these sessions followed that of the previous sessions: the stakeholders were asked to spend 15 minutes in small groups writing post-it notes outlining the specific issues, and then a 30-minute facilitated discussion was held in plenary. The participants were split into two groups (based on their preference) to generate post-it notes for the two first case studies, but the two corresponding discussions were held in plenary and included all participants. All participants took part in both idea generation and discussion for the third case. The thematic summaries below represent a combination of the written notes made during the sessions and post-hoc assessment of the key points raised on the post-it notes.

CS1: SPECIFIC NEEDS/OPPORTUNITIES RELATING TO SALMONELLA DUBLIN

- Working well
 - Data pathways are clear and well established.
 - Farm-level *Salmonella* Dublin statuses are publicly available online, although the underlying data that creates these statuses are not public.
 - If they suspect an active *Salmonella* Dublin infection, farmers have a legal and moral duty to inform other farmers they trade with, regardless of status.
- Challenges
 - Not all data are contained in a database – farmers can opt out of registering results of voluntary samples.
 - Ownership of and use of the data are not entirely clear to all stakeholders.
 - Not possible to combine with human data.
 - Variation in motivation for voluntary samples creates bias in prevalence estimates, particularly as some farmers may fear being penalised if voluntary samples come back positive. In some cases, these samples are deliberately sent to foreign laboratories to avoid this, but then the samples do not enter Danish databases.
- Solutions
 - It has previously been a requirement to register voluntary samples – restoring this legislation may help reduce bias, although it should remain possible to do consulting work without the requirement to register all results.
 - A political decision has been made to eradicate the disease, so the best strategy to achieve this should be followed.
 - Allowing anonymisation of sample results may help to reduce national-level bias in prevalence estimation.

CS2: SPECIFIC NEEDS/OPPORTUNITIES RELATING TO AFRICAN SWINE FEVER

- Working well

- Animal movement data, along with records of carcass collection and specific pathogen free status of farms, is made available to researchers working with ASF models.
 - Daily mortality is legally required to be recorded at farm level, although these data are typically not shared with the authorities or researchers as they are considered highly sensitive.
 - The disease also occurs outside Denmark, so we can use international experiences to inform our approach.
- Challenges
 - Access to relevant data outside of Denmark is very difficult. We lack information on denominators (farm locations, animal numbers) and there is typically a long time lag before cases are reported.
 - Risk pathways have missing data at crucial steps.
 - There is a massive potential financial penalty to finding ASF-positive wild boar in Denmark, so carcasses that are washed up on Danish beaches are typically not tested.
 - ASF test data are not well digitalised – there are severe challenges with linking the database holding test results to other databases.
 - Clinical surveillance data (overall sensitivity and specificity among farms) and data on farm-level biosecurity are not available to authorities or researchers.
 - Solutions
 - Work needs to be done to streamline integration of ASF test results into relevant databases.
 - We should be careful to only implement new systems/requirements for registration at farm level if there is a strong reason to believe it will improve things.

CS3: SPECIFIC NEEDS/OPPORTUNITIES RELATING TO ANTIMICROBIAL USAGE

- Working well
 - The data are extremely well described and publicly available via VetStat.
 - The original VetStat database/system was used as an example/motivation for evolution of policy at EU level – this is something to be proud of.
 - Although the data are imperfect, they can be used to benchmark vets.
 - Denmark in general is a leader in responsible usage of antimicrobials, and part of the reason for this is VetStat and the “yellow card” system for pig farms.
 - Responsible usage of antimicrobials in livestock helps to control the problem of antimicrobial resistance in livestock.
- Challenges
 - It is very important to understand the reason for collection of data when using it for other purposes, e.g. benchmarking.
 - Although availability of aggregated data is good, it is more challenging to obtain data at farm level.

- Accuracy of the recordings is not always known due to challenges in the responsibilities for checking/correcting errors. This also differs between species, for example checking accuracy is easier in pigs and more difficult in poultry/aquaculture.
 - Responsible usage of antimicrobials in livestock was originally motivated to help reduce problems with antimicrobial resistance in humans, but the effect on this has not been sufficiently demonstrated/documentated.
- Solutions
 - EU progress on reporting requirements is positive as it encourages vets to think more carefully about appropriate usage of antimicrobials, although there is a risk of deliberate mis-recording to justify use of a particular product.
 - The more the data are used, the more problems/mistakes are found and corrected.
 - It would be good to ensure that all relevant changes in regulations/procedures are recorded in the database along with the data (all legislation can be found at <https://www.retsinformation.dk> but a large amount of work is needed to select only the relevant information).
 - Documented responsible usage of antimicrobials helps Denmark to compete within international markets – this should be better communicated to farmers.

Conclusions

The overall consensus from the workshop was that Denmark has a strong tradition of collaboration on issues relating to livestock, and that the relevant data are typically of high quality and readily available in comparison to most other countries. The antimicrobial usage data registry VetStat is a particular success story, as well as an example that has set the standard across the EU. However, a number of issues were identified that represent obstacles to efficient digitalisation in some areas.

The issue of motivation for those entering data (i.e. vets and farmers) was a recurring theme. Several stakeholders noted that data entry takes resources, and that farmers invest a great deal of time and effort into ensuring that their data are accurately reflected in the relevant databases. These activities are obligatory for keepers of livestock, but it was felt that providing more positive motivation and feedback to farmers could encourage them to invest more proactively in these activities, which would potentially lead to higher standards of data quality. Ensuring that farmers are not required to enter the same data in multiple places was also identified as a key area for improvement - this could be accomplished by centralising data entry via a single unified data entry portal that would first cross-check entered data for inconsistencies and then distribute the digitised data to the necessary databases. A number of potential avenues for motivation were also suggested, including financial incentives, but the majority of stakeholders felt that improving communication and knowledge feedback to farmers is key. This can be as simple as examples of what the data is used for at national level, but ideally should also include provision of tools and information that can be of use on farm. This reflects the importance of the last step in the data lifecycle, which stakeholders feel is often neglected by researchers. Several stakeholders also highlighted the importance of understanding the origins of data when working with databases at higher levels, to avoid misunderstandings in terms of applicability of certain datasets to different problems. In many cases, the full understanding of databases lies with a small number of critical

staff members, which causes concerns for a potential loss of institutional knowledge if/when these individuals retire. The lack of documentation of databases was also highlighted as a related concern.

Another recurring theme was data sharing and data security. The Danish approach places emphasis on many types of data being publicly available, including CHR data (via the online interface at <http://chr.fvst.dk>) and VetStat data (via the online interface at <http://vetstat.fvst.dk>), with environmental protection legislation mandating that many other data sources are also, at least in theory, in the public domain. However, it was felt that this is one area where digitalisation has become more difficult in recent years, partly due to the uncertainty surrounding the application of GDPR to livestock data. Challenges include obtaining farm-level identifiers to facilitate merging different databases at farm level, as well as obtaining data from industry partners where commercial interests are at odds with public access regulations. Many stakeholders highlighted an urgent need for standardised data sharing agreements and procedures, taking into account both the legal and technical challenges involved in sharing data securely, in particular between different livestock sectors. This is relevant both to collaboration within Denmark (in particular with regards to CS1) and to collaboration at international level (in particular with regards to CS2).

Next steps

The DigiVet project runs until the end of 2023. The results of this workshop will be used to inform activities within Work Package 2, particularly the development of technical tools to facilitate data sharing. The findings will be shared within the DigiVet team and thereby contribute to the direction of development for all case studies. Following completion of Work Package 2 activities, the next step of the project will be workshops within Work Package 3. These workshops will explore the use of data digitalisation tools developed in the project in relation to case study 1 (African swine fever; UK workshop), case study 2 (*Salmonella* Dublin; Denmark workshop) and antimicrobial usage (Sweden workshop).

Appendices

APPENDIX 1: PARTICIPANTS AND AFFILIATIONS

Nineteen stakeholders (five male and fourteen female) participated from the following organisations:

- Five from the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (FVST).
- One from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU).
- Four from SEGES Innovation.
- Three from the Danish Agriculture and Food Council (L&F).
- Six from the University of Copenhagen.

In addition, six DigiVet team members / helpers (five male and one female) were present; five from the University of Copenhagen and one from the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration.

APPENDIX 2: MEETING AGENDA

DigiVet Workshop 2023-01-12, Festsalen, Nationalmuseet, Ny Vestergade 10, 1471 København K.

9.30-10.00: Arrival, tea/coffee and croissants

10.00-10.15: Introduction to DigiVet and the workshop

10.15-10.45: Round table introductions (1 min each)

10.45-12.00: Brainstorming and discussion (1):
What is working well and what challenges do we have with livestock data?

12.00-12.30: Lunch and tea/coffee

12.30-13.45: Brainstorming and discussion (2):
What are the root causes and potential solutions for the problems we face?

13.45-14.45: Brief tour of a selected exhibit at the museum, followed by tea/coffee

14.45-15.30: Brainstorming and discussion (3):
 Group A: *Specific needs/opportunities relating to Salmonella Dublin*
 Group B: *Specific needs/opportunities relating to African Swine Fever*

15.30-15.45: Tea/coffee/cake

15.45-16.30: Brainstorming and discussion (4):
Specific needs/opportunities relating to Antimicrobial Usage

16.30-17.00: Summary and thanks

Digivet: digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

Workshop Information sheet 2023

This workshop information sheet applies to the workshop about digitalisation of livestock data, including stakeholders from the Denmark, held at the National museum on 12th January 2023. It is part of a project called “Digivet: Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health”. The workshop is undertaken by researchers at the University of Copenhagen in conjunction with partners at the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, James Hutton Institute, University of Glasgow, University of Edinburgh, and the Swedish National Veterinary Institute. The project is funded by Nordforsk: a body which funds Nordic research and cooperation. The aims of the workshop are to:

- 1) Discuss the practical, ethical and governance issues surrounding the use and distribution of livestock data between industry and academic partners.
- 2) Identify which areas of livestock digitalisation are working well, and which areas present challenges.
- 3) Elaborate on the challenges encountered and devise potential solutions where possible.
- 4) Discuss specific challenges relating to our three case studies of foodborne disease, antimicrobial usage, and contagious diseases of livestock.

Participants’ data will be stored securely and will only be accessible to the project team for the purposes of organising the workshop. The workshop is conducted under the Chatham House Rule i.e. we make notes of discussion topics during the workshop and produce a report which will be circulated to attendees, but these notes/report will NOT reveal the identity or affiliation of individuals in relation to specific comments.

If you wish to ask us any questions, please contact us by email on: md@sund.ku.dk

Your participation is voluntary, and you may leave the meeting at any time. All data collected will be treated with full confidentiality and in line with relevant data protection legislation.

Many thanks for your participation,

Matt Denwood (University of Copenhagen)

Privacy Notice

The University of Copenhagen (“us” or “we”) will use your personal data for the purposes of the research undertaken in this project “**Digivet: Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health**” (“**The Project**”) in accordance with our privacy notice at <https://informationssikkerhed.ku.dk/english/protection-of-information-privacy/privacy-policy/>. Our lawful basis for processing your personal data is that this is necessary for publicly funded research we undertake as a task in the public interest. We are the data controller for the personal data collected for the purposes of above project. We will collect and use personal data in line with relevant data protection legislation including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Notes will be taken from the workshop to allow us the best opportunity to retrieve information for our study. Personal data (names, contact details, job field/role) will be linked to consent forms, but contributions to the workshop will be recorded anonymously. All data will be stored in restricted access files on the server and/or secure cloud-based storage used by the University of Copenhagen and research partners at the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration, James Hutton Institute, University of Glasgow, University of Edinburgh, and the Swedish National Veterinary Institute.

Contributions to the workshop will be anonymised through removal of names and other directly identifying information and published only in summarised form. However, summaries and other research outputs may include information on respondent’s background (e.g., academic, regulatory, policy-related, industry) and/or some original wording may be retained therein through which the individual may be indirectly identifiable.

We may share pseudonymised transcripts with a professional transcriber who has an appropriate contract in place with the James Hutton Institute to ensure that participants’ data is held securely and protected adequately.

We will retain your personal data only for as long this is necessary to fulfil the purposes and produce outputs for the Project and will delete/destroy it afterwards. Our main privacy notice will explain what we do with personal data in more detail as well as your rights. Or, if you have any queries about your personal data you can contact us by email at md@sund.ku.dk

Matt Denwood

University of Copenhagen

Email: md@sund.ku.dk

Telephone: +45 35 33 23 07